

Annual Plan

2023 – 2024

1 Message from the Director	2
2 Governance	3
3 Programme of Work	4
3.1 The Data Facility	4
3.1.1 CBS Microdata Access	4
3.1.2 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer	5
3.1.3 ODISSEI Portal	7
3.2 The Observatory	8
3.2.1 ODISSEI Data Collection Committee	8
3.2.2 Historical Sample of the Netherlands	9
3.2.3 National Twin Registry	10
3.3 The Laboratory	11
3.3.1 Distributed Analytics	11
3.3.2 Automated Linkage	12
3.3.3 The LISS panel	13
3.4 The Hub	14
3.4.1 Community Management	14
3.4.2 Educational Programme	15
3.4.3 ODISSEI Social Data Science	16
3.4.4 eScience Grants	18
3.4.5 Benchmarking	19
4 Financial Plan 2022-2023	20
5 Key Performance Indicators	22
Previous Risks	24
Current Risks	25

1 Message from the Director

With much pride, we see ODISSEI entering maturity. Many of its facilities are fully operational and ODISSEI has developed a vibrant community of users. Over the past year, the ODISSEI Portal has been further developed, and the usage of the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer has increased, and we have been granted SSHOC-NL, a new NWO Roadmap grant, which will open up exciting avenues for ODISSEI development. We are particularly proud of last year's Community Conference. With over 300 participants and 50 high-quality presentations, the event brought together a vibrant ODISSEI community that has grown over the past years.

We are entering the final period of the current Roadmap project - *Better Infrastructure, Better Science, Better Society* - and in this annual plan, we outline how ODISSEI will continue to provide important facilities for the scientific community. With a few tasks already successfully completed and others well on track, we are confident that ODISSEI will deliver the promise of the Roadmap project and will further consolidate ODISSEI's position as a leader in the social sciences regarding access to data, tools, high-performance computing capacity, and expertise.

A number of initiatives will be continued in the coming year. Technological developments aimed at removing barriers to microdata usage will benefit the whole community. The OSSC will be used to test groundbreaking developments in privacy-preserving techniques. Implementation of the access broker will help the Portal reach its full potential, while the benchmark platform will further expand opportunities for predicting outcomes in people's lives .

All this work will serve the greater goal of helping the social science community improve the empirical basis of their research. This summer we will welcome a new cohort of ODISSEI Summer School for Computational Social Science (SICSS) participants, who will delve into topics such as network analysis, machine learning, benchmarking, and the ethics of big data. We also look forward to our next Community Conference on 2nd November 2023, which we hope, will again be a celebration of the social sciences in the Netherlands.

Pearl Dykstra
Director, ODISSEI

2 Governance

ODISSEI now consists of **45 member organisations** who have all signed the participants agreement and committed their financial contribution to ODISSEI until 2024, the end of the Roadmap project.

The **Supervisory Board** consists of Pieter Hooimeijer (DSW, chair), Carlo Schuengel (DSW), Henk van der Kolk (DSW), Viola Angelini (DEB), Hanneke Imbens (Statistics Netherlands), Helga de Valk (KNAW/NWO institutes and E-infrastructures), and Pauline Flore (public research institutes).

The **Management Board** consists of nine members: Pearl Dykstra (EUR, Chair and Director), Tom Emery (EUR, Deputy Director), Dorret Boomsma (VU), Jessica Piotrowski (UvA), Marcel Das (Centerdata), Ran van den Boom (Statistics Netherlands), Annette Langedijk (SURF), Rob van Nieuwpoort (NLeSC), Anja Smit (DANS), and Jacco van Ossenbruggen (VU). The Management Board meets monthly to discuss and evaluate the program of work.

The Coordination Team is composed of Pearl Dykstra (Director), Tom Emery (Deputy Director), Lucas van der Meer (Chief Technical Officer), Kasia Karpinska (Scientific Manager), Suze Zijlstra (Community Manager), Thomas Groen (Community Manager), Angelica Maineri (Data Manager), Sofia den Haan (Project Management Officer) and Emilio Cammarata (Trainee).

Suze Zijlstra will leave ODISSEI as of July 2023. A selection procedure for a Project Manager position is currently open and a new employee is expected to start after the summer.

An **International Advisory Board** has been established including Julia Lane (New York University), Melinda Mills (University of Oxford), Sally Wyatt (Maastricht University), and Amy O'Hara (Georgetown University). Due to travel restrictions the board has yet to meet in person, but a virtual meeting took place in May 2021 and a further meeting is planned for late 2023.

3 Programme of Work

3.1 The Data Facility

3.1.1 CBS Microdata Access

ODISSEI stimulates the use of the rich microdata at Statistics Netherlands (CBS), particularly amongst early career researchers and first-time users. In early 2023, ODISSEI launched its annual call to facilitate access to microdata from Statistics Netherlands free of charge for researchers at ODISSEI member organisations (so-called Microdata Access Grants, MAG). Around six projects will be granted in Summer 2023. The amounts awarded are small with an average amount of € 7,500 but the impact of access is large, and these projects would not be possible without them. The Microdata Access Discount (MAD) which has been administered in collaboration with Statistics Netherlands will be continued until the end of 2023, with a budget of **€ 125,000**. The programme has achieved its goal of broadening the access to microdata and an increasing number of projects participated in the programme over the years, leading to decreasing rates of the discount. A full list of projects that received the discount until its closure is available on the [ODISSEI website](#).

CBS will redirect the remaining resources, **€ 520,000** until the end of the Roadmap project, towards measures that will improve the performance of the remote access environment. This self-service portal, which would allow users to arrange many elements of their RA projects; will receive further investments in the automatic disclosure checks for standard output and improvement of the administrative processes in Microdata Services. Part of the resources will be also allocated towards additional Microdata Access Grants (a total of **€ 75,000** for 10 grants to be awarded in 2024).

Genetic and environmental determinants of socioeconomic status in the Lifelines cohort

Inequality in income and wealth is pervasive and growing in the Netherlands and other developed countries. Research in social science genetics has demonstrated that genes, socioeconomic environmental factors and their interaction each contribute substantially to the determination of socioeconomic outcomes. However, the environmental pathways through which genetic endowments translate into socioeconomic status (SES) are poorly understood. This study combines measures of genetic endowments in the Dutch Lifelines cohort with high-quality CBS microdata on SES (income, wealth, job type and education), based on administrative records. This allows researchers to 1) estimate causal genetic effects (by conditioning on the parental genotype), 2) estimate causal environmental effects (by exploring natural experiments), and 3) explore extremely rich measures of SES, in the study of gene-by-environment interplay.

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3.1.2 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

Statistics Netherlands and SURF transitioned the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer (OSSC) to the new national Supercomputer Snellius, in May 2022. This facility is a global first enabling the analysis of highly sensitive administrative data that is linked to data from social surveys and other sources in a secure HPC environment. The ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer provides the fastest computing capacity in the Netherlands via the national supercomputer and obeys the highest standards for data protection both legally and technically. In May 2022, the OSSC demonstrated its security by passing a penetration test performed by the digital security company Secura^{1,2}.

Operation of the OSSC will cost € 215,294 in 2022-2024 (period of 1.5 years, until the end of the Roadmap project) which is exclusively for SURF. A further € 64,000 is planned for the development of the OSSC environment for research, which is shared between SURF and CBS. This includes the cost adaptations to ensure the OSSC can service all member organisations, automatic reservation system and support of users. The OSSC was formally launched in October 2020 and now has capacity to support 15 projects per year. There have been delays in initiating projects due to the transfer of the OSSC from Cartesius to Snellius but these delays are now resolved. Interest in the OSSC has been considerable and comes from a wide variety of member organisations, as well as from organisations that are not ODISSEI members. Through 2023-24 it is hoped that a further seven projects will be supported in their implementation and usage of OSSC with the Coordination Team monitoring progress. The OSSC team will finalise the sustainability plan and report on estimated demand for specific OSSC services.

Using synthetic data to study special educational needs

The main goal of the project is to develop a synthetic data framework using artificial intelligence technologies while concurrently exploring ethical-legal perspectives in the trade-off between data privacy and the potential utilization of synthetic representations. The project focuses on: 1) the quality of synthetically generated data to real-world data as a function of privacy cost, 2) the quality of preservation of multi-attribute relations in the face of increased individual variation, and 3) the utility of synthetic data in certain kinds of social science research. Together with our collaborators from the Inspectorate of Education, Netherlands Initiative for Education Research (NRO), and CBS, the researchers from University of Maastricht conduct several regression analyses on both real and synthetic data for studying if and how students with Special Emotional Needs (SEN) affect non-SEN students.

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¹ www.secura.com/penetration-testing

² Photo credit: <https://unsplash.com/photos/FnA5pAzqhMM>

3.2 The Observatory

3.2.1 ODISSEI Data Collection Committee

The ODISSEI Data Collection Committee facilitates collaboration and aims to transition the long-standing data collections into a coherent and sustainable future in which they are well placed within a more diverse and dynamic data landscape. ODISSEI ensures Dutch participation in cross-national data collections works to identify critical gaps in the data landscape and allocate resources to sustain longitudinal data collections. The Data Collection Committee has supported data collections transition to sustainable operational models. Four members have been appointed: Marike Knoef (Chair), Gerbert Kraaykamp, Janine van der Maat, and Bella Struminskaya.

ODISSEI finances Dutch participation in European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERIC) and surveys of key strategic importance. In 2023-24, ODISSEI is financing the position of CTO of Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (€ 50,000) and the completion of the latest round of ESS (€ 172,561). ODISSEI will also pay the Dutch contribution for the Luxembourg Income Study (€ 30,000) and International Social Survey Programme (€ 40,000).

As Chair of the Data Collection Committee, Marike Knoef also oversees a data scout, Marco Stam, who identifies new sources of data for integration within ODISSEI (the ODISSEI Data Portal, linkage to CBS Microdata, use of secure data environments etc), especially data that has not been collected for research purposes and particularly in the fields of Law and Economics which are currently under-represented within the ODISSEI framework. Marco works with potential data providers and existing ODISSEI services to facilitate access to such data sets, ensure their adequate documentation and promote their usage. In 2023-24 this work will cost € 26,238.

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3.2.2 Media Content Analysis Lab

The ODISSEI Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL) will offer opportunities for systematic analysis of large corpora of digital media content. MCAL tackles the major challenge of digital text analysis whereby copyright and GDPR restrictions make it very hard to share media content data by providing a workbench for researchers where they can share data and analyses with strict rights management, without the need to read or export the data themselves. Currently, several Dutch initiatives exist that facilitate retrieval, storage, and analysis of media content (i.e. the infrastructure for content analysis [INCA] at the University of Amsterdam (Trilling et al., 2018), and the Amsterdam Content Analysis Toolkit [AMCaT] at VU Amsterdam (Van Atteveldt et al., 2014). Their use, however, requires considerable programming skills and is currently tailored to a limited set of applications.

Through MCAL, the large amount of longitudinal media content data (i.e. online news data; social media data, specific coded datasets) currently available in various Dutch universities will be made available to researchers at ODISSEI member organisations. To achieve this, the task is constructing a FAIR Linked Open Data Model in collaboration with the FAIR Expertise Hub and [Triply](#). This will allow for Media Content Analysis tools, data and workflows to be linked and integrated within the wider ODISSEI ecosystem.

The work will be conducted by post-docs appointed at WUR and UvA budgeted for € 144,059.

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3.2.3 National Twin Registry

The work conducted by the National Twin Register (NTR) focuses on linking biomedical and cognitive data with the wider ODISSEI infrastructure through proof-of-concept projects within the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer and integrating and consolidating existing research on pedigrees across microdata projects at Statistics Netherlands. The work forms a key bridge to the work conducted in the Consortium on Individual Development (CID)³ and BBMRI (Netherlands Biobank Research Facility)⁴ and consists of two tasks.

The first task is to broaden the scope of record linkage of cohort data and CBS data conducted as part of the OSSC pilot to include multiple external cohorts. The goal is to build on the procedures set up by the NTR teams and develop a standard operating procedure (SOP) within the new national SuperComputer, Snellius, for linking and analysing multiple external data sources with CBS data at once. This will allow for the pooling of cohorts and subsequent linkage to CBS microdata, greatly increasing the diversity of research questions that can be answered about specific sub-populations. This work should be completed in autumn 2023.

The second task defines a thorough network of family ties in the CBS data by including the classifications of genetic resemblance and creating a standardised method of defining family ties. Possibilities for differentiating between mono- and dizygotic twins based on CBS microdata or other external data sources (e.g. perined.nl, pargaopenbaredatabank.nl) will be developed. The budget for this work in 2023-24 will be € 92,398.

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³ individualdevelopment.nl

⁴ bbmri.nl

3.3 The Laboratory

3.3.2 Automated Linkage

This task applies innovations in information science to enhance the work conducted within the Portal. The ODISSEI Portal makes research datasets findable by providing an advanced search interface on the data records describing these data sets. We refer to these records as the metadata. The better the quality of these metadata records, the better the Portal's functionality. While the main responsibility for providing high-quality metadata lies with the data owners and data providers in the project, (semi) automatic enrichment of metadata of ODISSEI datasets can also help to improve the metadata used in the Portal. For example, in this task CBS metadata is enriched with controlled vocabularies such as [ELSSST](#) to make the portal easier to navigate for scientists.

This task designs and develops methods and techniques for (semi) automatic enrichment of metadata of ODISSEI datasets. Special focus is on improving metadata for sensitive datasets, to help researchers 1) find these datasets and 2) help them assess their applicability to their research before requesting access to the actual data. Another example is the codification of data access conditions and licensing. Information about data constraints has been extracted from the licence and policy agreements applied to the data. This includes information such as whether the data can be used for academic or commercial purposes, if the data can be downloaded, if the data allows for derivative works, how attribution must be given to original work. Such information is not intrinsically present in the metadata, and therefore this process significantly enhances the interoperability and reusability of data. Crucially, this codification makes the licensing and data access requirements machine actionable and has the potential to greatly improve the efficiency of data access across ODISSEI in the future.

For the year 2023-24, the budget of this task is € 100,628 which is exclusively for project staff.

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3.3.3 The LISS panel

The LISS panel, managed by Centerdata, consists of some 7,000 individuals from approximately 4,500 households. The panel is a representative sample of the adult population in the Netherlands. In May 2023, ODISSEI launched the sixth round of the **LISS Grant**. The calls are exceptionally popular. Successful projects are showcased on the ODISSEI website⁵ and generate considerable press attention. The call closes on 21 September 2023. All proposals that meet the eligibility criteria are assessed by the Centerdata team for feasibility. They are then submitted for peer-review. Reviewers' scores will be returned by the end of November and the decision announced by mid-December. The projects will commence from February 2024. These calls cost **€ 190,000** for 2023-24 and covers two separate rounds of calls.

In addition to the LISS Grants, ODISSEI will provide a **€ 500,000 subsidy to the LISS panel**. This budget will be used for the maintenance of the LISS panel in 2023-2024 (period of one year and a half). These fixed annual costs include personnel costs for panel management, subscription of broadband connection for panel members with initially no internet access, maintenance of hardware on loan to panel members, server and software licence costs, and incentive costs for updating background variables and activation of 'sleeping' panel members (as to avoid attrition). A further **€ 40,000** is made available for improving the LISS metadata catalogue for variable level integration in the portal.

As a recognition to ODISSEI of the provided subsidy, Centerdata provides a 20% discount for using the LISS panel to projects from ODISSEI member organisations. In 2022-23, the ODISSEI coordination team evaluated the performance of the LISS call and its ability to stimulate innovative research and widen access. The minor amendments implemented to the LISS call for 2022 (the proposals from larger groups of researchers were more explicitly encouraged) and were evaluated. Following the evaluation, the explicit encouragement for submissions from larger groups of researchers was reversed because it privileged those in more senior position .

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⁵ <https://odissei-data.nl/en/2022/12/liss-grants-2022-announcement/>

3.4 The Hub

3.4.1 Community Management

ODISSEI has 45 member organisations and is open for others to join. There are a lot of potential users whose research would benefit from the infrastructure ODISSEI offers. Some have heard of the possibilities, but do not know ODISSEI can support them in using the infrastructure. Others already use ODISSEI but are not aware of all the infrastructure has to offer. It is important that they continue to stay involved or use the infrastructure more widely. The goal of Community Management is, first, to ensure that all potential users in relevant disciplines have high-quality knowledge of ODISSEI so they can understand its use and importance (**inform**). Researchers should be encouraged to take the next step in engagement with ODISSEI (**involve**). Those who are already involved should be stimulated to stay involved to broaden and deepen their involvement (**engage**). For that purpose, Community Management will deploy a wide range of activities:

Inform:

- Newsletter
- Website
- Posts on Twitter and LinkedIn.
- Podcast series

Involve:

- Annual conference
- Task Insights meetings
- Active Slack Community
- Lunch lecture series

Engage:

- Grant information workshops
- ODISSEI Introduction presentations
- Partner event

The community management costs for 2023-2024 include the costs of the ODISSEI coordination team for 18 months (€ 497,370), all events including the ODISSEI Community Conference (€ 50,000), Community Management of ASReview (€ 45,000) and material costs for travel, events, and training across the project (€ 148,000).

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3.4.2 Educational Programme

In 2023 ODISSEI is organising its second [ODISSEI Summer School in Computational Social Science](#) in collaboration with [SICSS](#). This summer school will provide 21 participants with two full weeks of intensive training in network analysis, machine learning, benchmark approaches and the ethics of big data (see section 3.4.5). The program of the summer school will be delivered by the Social Data Science (SoDa) team, the Benchmarking team, the eScience Center, and Coordination Team. The summer school provides the access and training necessary to use complex elements of the ODISSEI infrastructure. ODISSEI has the summer school accredited with ECTS points for graduate students in cooperation with the Erasmus Graduate School of Social Sciences and the Humanities (EGSH). In 2024, a repeat and potential expansion of the summer school is planned.

The summer school complements a broader programme of workshops that is geared towards using specific ODISSEI facilities, with workshops tailored to potential and current users of ODISSEI facilities, such as the Microdata Access Grant and Discount, the LISS panel Grant and the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer. These workshops aim to inform researchers of the ins and outs of ODISSEI facilities and lower the threshold for submitting a project proposal. The programme is developed in collaboration with, and executed by or together with, several ODISSEI partners: Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS), CBS, Centerdata, Netherlands eScience Center (NLLeSC) and SURF.

The team also works with the graduate schools and ODISSEI member organisations to coordinate existing efforts and where feasible identify and help address gaps in the existing provision of training and education in the Dutch Computational Social Science community. For 2023-24, the educational team will deliver approximately 5 workshops aimed at using the ODISSEI infrastructure and focused on thematic areas of interest such as geospatial analysis or network analysis. The costs of operating the ODISSEI educational programme for 2023-24 are € 60,000 and include the costs of coordination and resources for hosting events, including the ODISSEI Summer School.

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3.4.3 ODISSEI Social Data Science

The Social Data Science (SoDa) team bridges the gap between applied social scientists and the data, computing, and analytical infrastructure provided by ODISSEI. They seek out short-term collaborative projects with social scientists across ODISSEI member organisations, uniquely leverage ODISSEI's infrastructure to answer novel substantive questions, and build expertise in computational social science. These projects result not only in 'traditional' publications, but also in open-source reusable code that can be used for teaching purposes or as a starting point for other projects. The team supports researchers using other components of the infrastructure such as the OSSC, Microdata, eScience or LISS. In 2022-23, SoDa took on eight projects and has capacity to take on further projects and collaborations through 2023-24. Also, the SoDa team will continue offering SoDa traineeships, a programme aimed at early career researchers, who are offered a paid appointment with the team, to develop a set skills by working on a project under the supervision of the SoDa team member.

The SoDa team is growing rapidly and consists of Daniel Oberski (PI), Erik-Jan van Kesteren (Team Leader), Jonathan de Bruin, Javier Garcia Bernardo, Parisa Zahedi, Shiva Nadi, and Raoul Schram. This team has the capacity to increase the number of projects conducted during 2023-2024 and costs € 253,592.

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Examples of SoDa Projects 2022-2023

Policy intervention assessment in primary schools. SoDa team is helping to compute individual causal effects of a policy intervention in primary schools in Rotterdam. For this, we are exploring the use of advanced quasi-experimental methods such as synthetic controls.

Machine learning pipeline for early life opportunity. SoDa team collaborate on a creation of a data analysis and machine learning pipeline for the project "Kansrijke start", which aims to investigate which markers in the first 1000 days since conception are predictive of adverse events later in life.

Computational models for word and non-word associations. This project focuses on computation modelling people's intuitions about various associations of both real words and non-words (e.g., novel words or company names) for the Dutch language. The project will result in an easy-to-use openly available application in which (non-)words can be analyzed for various associations that they may evoke as well as give a list of semantically similar words.

Trust in public institutions. In this project the SoDa team creates a pipeline and dashboard to evaluate how trust on European public institutions evolves during pandemic.

Benchmarking for social science. SoDa team helped to design and set up a benchmark for a social data science challenge at the end of the SICSS-ODISSEI summer school. The benchmark was based on microdata from Statistics Netherlands.

Synthetic register data for open science. SoDa team created a workflow using existing software packages to generate synthetic datasets for the Statistics Netherlands microdata architecture. These synthetic datasets can then be used as example datasets when sharing analyses (but not original data) with researchers.

3.4.4 eScience Grants

In this task grants are provided for computational social science to support the use of the data infrastructure developed across ODISSEI. These grants provide hours from eScience Research Engineers (RSEs) employed at the eScience center to collaborate with social scientists

and enhance their research by exploiting digital technologies. The grants structure offered in collaboration with the eScience Center has changed and will no longer be offered in an open competition structure. Instead, the budget will be allocated to projects that meet strategic goals of ODISSEI. Those projects will be identified by the ODISSEI Coordination Team in consultation with the eScience Center. In the period 2023-2024, € 191,833 will be allocated to this goal. The first project assigned the RSE support is the synthetic data project by University of Maastricht, which will be executed in the OSSC (for details see 3.1.2.).

The collaboration with the SoDa team will continue to ensure that the researchers are well positioned to apply for a full project in the eScience center open calls. Vice versa, successful eScience projects may lead to new SoDa followup projects as well. In addition to the open call for proposals, eScience Center can be engaged in ad-hoc projects throughout ODISSEI such as the ODISSEI Summer School and consulting on OSSC projects.

Example eScience project: The role of gender and ethnicity in PhD-to-Labor-Market linkages

Gender and ethnic inequality in the labor market is a key societal issue. Some groups are overrepresented in rewarding jobs, whereas others face difficulties finding their footing. The academic labor market is not excluded from such patterns: women and ethnic minorities are underrepresented among professors. Such reproduced advantage instead of distributed opportunity causes individual scientists to face structural career barriers. With big data of nearly all Dutch PhDs (1990-2021) the project considers how gender, ethnicity, and social networks influence labor market outcomes. The project focuses on careers outside academia, by cross-linking PhD data to non-science career databases to explain gender and ethnic labor market differences of Dutch PhD-recipients.

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3.4.5 Benchmarking

Benchmarking is about creating a system of reference, in which various models that address the same task can be compared, in order to be able to analyse the strength and weaknesses of various approaches and gain new insights. For computer scientists, benchmarks provide a standardised way to validate predictive models that have proven to be able to detect major breakthroughs, like deep learning. For example, when Geoffrey Hinton submitted his convolutional neural network AlexNet to the ImageNet challenge (a computer vision benchmark) it showed a dramatic increase in performance, which boosted the field of neural networks and artificial intelligence in general.

The aim of this task is to design and set-up a benchmark for social sciences that addresses a real-world problem that social scientists are working on and preferably draws from various data sources. In 2022 this task deployed benchmarking challenges using ODISSEI infrastructure, which was the first social science benchmark to utilise linked administrative data. To achieve this, a benchmarking challenge was embedded within the ODISSEI Summer School. In the second week of the summer school, participants were separated into small teams and given access to CBS microdata and challenged to predict several individual level outcomes (such as unemployment). In the 2023 iteration of the summer school, the participants will be asked to predict the fertility using LISS panel data and administrative data. The topic of the challenge was set out in collaboration with dr. Gert Stulp from University of Groningen.

In 2023-2024 the cost of coordinating the benchmarking project will be **€ 34,818** for the year, and run until the end of the roadmap project with a challenge embedded in each subsequent ODISSEI Summer School. The work will be led by Paulina Pankowska in collaboration with the coordination team and SoDa. Additionally, ODISSEI will invest **€ 37,000** in benchmarking infrastructure: software that will be the starter kit 'Software-as-a-service' infrastructure for benchmarking, which will facilitate support, standardise and ease the design and implementation of benchmarks for the social science. The work will be executed by software company EYRA.

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4 Financial Plan 2023-2024

ODISSEI aligned the reporting schedule of (a) the Task Leaders to the Management Board, (b) the Management Board to the Supervisory Board, and (c) ODISSEI to NWO. For this reason, the financial year runs from 1 July to 30 June. The table below summarises the financial allocations requested by the task leaders and approved by the Management Board for the year 2023-2024. As this is the final reporting period for the ODISSEI Roadmap project, the task allocations include costs for an 18 month period up to December 31st 2024. This results in costs that are approximately 50% higher than previous years in tasks such as 1.1, 1.4 and 3.4 This is in line with the budget proposals in the initial roadmap application. For a specific description of each task and the use of its budget, please see section 3. The financial plan currently projects a 2% underspend which is available for contingencies in the final 18 months of the project.

Table 2 – Budget Plan for 2023-2024 (with 2020-21, 2021-22 & 2022-23 for reference)

	(in €)	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024
Data Facility		1,216,541	882,959	1,345,280	1,385,657
1.1 CBS Microdata		394,000	360,000	414,000	720,000
1.2 Use Cases		40,000	9,598	-	-
1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer		615,223	245,998	638,483	279,294
1.4 Portal		167,318	267,363	292,797	386,363
Observatory		376,666	1,188,031	721,135	555,256
2.1 Data collection		251,157	996,273	572,862	318,799
2.2 Media Content Analysis Lab		11,700	53,542	60,875	144,059
2.1 Historical Sample of NL		113,809	67,307	-	-
2.1 Netherlands Twin Register		-	70,909	87,398	92,398
Laboratory		391,661	708,682	462,501	863,575
3.1 Distributed Learning		49,862	65,141	98,583	32,947
3.2 Automatic Linking		70,909	72,398	93,918	100,628
3.4 LISS panel		260,000	520,000	270,000	730,000
3.4 Mass Online Experiments		10,890	51,143	-	-
Hub		572,639	776,453	924,451	1,317,613
4.1 Community management		222,843	474,000	495,610	740,370
4.2 Education		10,000	60,000	60,000	60,000
4.3 Social Data Science team		173,463	219,283	155,289	253,592
4.4 eScience Grants		166,333	-	191,833	191,833
4.5 Benchmarking		-	23,170	21,719	71,818

Total	2,557,507	3,556,125	3,453,367	4,122,101
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5 Key Performance Indicators

ODISSEI maintains a register of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that were initiated at the beginning of the current Roadmap period. Each year the current status of each KPI is reported upon and new targets are established. The KPIs are proposed by the Coordination Team and Management Board and amended and approved by the ODISSEI Supervisory Board to ensure continuity and alignment with regards to the specific and concrete aims of the project.

Table 3 - Key Performance Indicators

Indicator	Target	Current
Development		
Participation of all social science and economics faculties	All social science and 9 economics faculties to be full ODISSEI members by 2025	All social science faculties and 9 Economics faculties are members.
Participation in European projects	Active participation in at least two European Level projects by 2025	ODISSEI is now a partner in SoBigData Europe and investigating further projects.
International infrastructure collaborations	Formal collaboration with similar initiatives in UK, US, FR, and DE by 2024	Initial contact has been made with discussion of formalisation
Data Access & Analysis		
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations submitting a proposal	Receive project proposals from 10% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations	Currently approximately 7% of all researchers have submitted
Percentage of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations being granted a project	Provide access to 5% of researchers at ODISSEI member organisations by 2025	Currently 1% of all researchers have received a grant
Number of unique visitors to the ODISSEI Portal	No current target set (To be set in 2023)	None as Portal is still in development
Number of OSSC Projects per year	7 per year for 2022, 2023 and 2024	7 in 2023
Number of projects spanning more than 2 service providers	5 per year by 2025	6 projects in 2023
Financial		
Further successful funding applications	Participation in a successful 2022 Roadmap Application for SSH	2022 Roadmap proposal and SSO proposal submitted
Total amount committed by member organisations	By 2025, to receive continuation of existing commitments to 2029 as a minimum	Current contributions are perpetual but no commitments until 2029
Training & Education		

Number of attendees at training events and workshops	600 unique attendees at events per year	590 for 2022
Number of projects supported by Social Data Analytics Team (SoDa)	15 projects completed before end of 2024	15 projects acquired up to April 2023
Science & Technology		
Number of scientific papers describing the infrastructure	3 per year by 2025	2 in 2022
Number of peer-reviewed publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	30 per year by 2025	34 in 2021-2022
Number of citations received for publications derived from ODISSEI supported research projects	200 per year by 2025	320 in 2021-2022
Social and Economic Impact		
Number of datasets contributed by non-academic organisations	Five datasets from non-academic organisations accessible by 2025	2
Number of government agencies participating as member organisations	7 by 2025	6
Number of website visits	50,000 per year by 2025	37,426 in 2021-2022
Mentions in key policy documents	3 per year	Monitoring as of 2023
Press mentions of ODISSEI related research in the Netherlands	10 per year	Monitoring as of 2023
Communication		
Number of social media (e.g. Twitter, LinkedIn) subscribers	2,500 by 2025	1468 (50% growth per year, projected at 2,202 by 2025)
Number of newsletter subscribers	Total of 1,000 by 2025	1090 up to May 2023
Attracting New Talent		
Number of international scientists recruited by ODISSEI	20 by the end of 2024	Reported in 2024
Number of major grants using ODISSEI (e.g. NWO talent, MCSA, ERC etc)	5 per year	2 in 2023

6 Risk Register

The ODISSEI Risk register is designed to support the strategic planning and decision making of the Coordination Team, the Management Board, and the Supervisory Board. Risk assessments are always subjective but consolidating the risk assessments into a singular document can help identify common risks, differences in risk perceptions across the project and interdependent mitigation strategies. The full risk register appears at the end of this document and has been used to create an overview of the various challenges faced by ODISSEI.

The high probability, high impact risks for this year were identified by Task Leaders, the Coordination Team and the Management Board and listed in Table 4. All the risks have been explicitly discussed by the Management Board and are being actively monitored by task leaders and Coordination Team contacts. As the ODISSEI Roadmap project enters its last phase, the probability of many risks occurring reduces.

A core risk is in the OSSC, where the signing of several updated legal documents is substantially delayed. This resulted in having to postpone several OSSC projects. This issue was escalated at both CBS and SURF, now ensuring the involvement and availability of the organisations' highest legal councils. It is expected that the issue will be resolved in the coming months.

A second core risk is the alignment between the OSSC, Portal, SANE, and the wider ODISSEI ecosystem. Entering the last project phase, the increased need for alignment of the user processes has become clear. In addition, the importance and size of the OSSC justifies an end-of-project reevaluation of its user needs. To mitigate these risks, a SURF-ODISSEI sustainability strategy and an OSSC User evaluation will be developed by a joint working group between SURF and the ODISSEI Coordination Team. To oversee these developments, a new technical project manager overseeing all ODISSEI projects will be appointed at SURF, complementing the SURF-ODISSEI Research Partnership Lead.

Finally, a more intensive alignment between the LISS panel and the Portal team was needed, compared to what we expected at the beginning of the project. To tackle this issue, extra funds were freed to facilitate the integration and a joint working group will meet periodically to oversee these developments.

Table 4 - High Probability, High Impact Risks

<i>Task</i>		<i>Mitigation</i>
1.3	Delay in the signing of legal documents	Escalated to higher level; periodic project group meetings
1.3	Misalignment with wider ODISSEI ecosystem	A SURF-ODISSEI sustainability strategy and OSSC User evaluation will be developed.
3.3	Insufficient alignment with the Portal team	Joint working group; funds made available

Full Risk Register

Table 5 - Full Risk Register

Task	#	Risk	Prob ⁶	Imp ⁷	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
Data Facility						
1.1	1	Restrictions in the usage of CBS microdata, e.g., as a follow-up of the external investigation into the security of Microdata Services	1	3	Increase technical and procedural safety warrants so that the research process itself is not affected more than necessary	Legal
1.1	2	Increased usage to an extent that the MAD percentage to an undesirably low level, that might cause some members to consider leaving ODISSEI	2	2	After a careful consideration with users, the MAD will be terminated this year.	High Demand
1.1	3	Unequal usage of the MAD across scientific domains and categories of users	2	3	After a careful consideration with users, the MAD will be terminated this year.	Low Demand
1.1	4	The self-service portal is not feasible within time and budget	1	2	Propose smaller scale, stepwise innovations in agreement with the user council	Sustainability
1.3	1	Failure of Cartesius hardware/software could mean down time for OSSC	2	2	Build and migrate as soon as possible to Snellius.	Technical
1.3	2	Misalignment between SURF and CBS	2	3	The team will have periodic meetings	Coordination
1.3	3	Misalignment with wider ODISSEI ecosystem	3	3	A SURF-ODISSEI sustainability strategy will be developed.	Coordination
1.3	4	Too difficult OSSC user interface	2	2	Working on a graphic interface, education (Roadmap task 4.2)	Technical
1.3	5	Pentest results could cause delay on migration	2	2	Use Cartesius as long as possible	Technical
1.3	6	OSSC compatibility with Snellius reduced or lost due to changes	1	3	Include OSSC regression test during upgrades/changes	Technical
1.3	7	Delay in the signing of legal documents	3	3	Escalated to higher level; periodic project group meetings	Legal
1.4 ⁸	1	Not being able to hire and retain appropriate staff	1	3	Widely setting out vacancies, possibility to outsource the hiring.	Staffing
1.4	2	Misalignment (strategic or technical) between the partners	2	3	Bi-weekly, low-profile steering group and technical meetings	Coordination
1.4	3	Potential metadata providers not willing to or able to (automatically) share metadata, or to invest in altering metadata	2	3	Representatives in the ODISSEI Management Board. Cooperating with the ODISSEI Fieldwork Committee. Support and money available.	FAIR
1.4	4	Insufficient need for the Portal	1	3	Three-monthly user tests, presenting early versions at conferences, creating use cases, close collaboration with the social science research community.	Low Demand

⁶ Probability: 3 = high, 2 = medium, 1 = low

⁷ Impact

⁸ Including those of task 3.2, which is executed as one task

Task	#	Risk	Prob ⁶	Imp ⁷	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
1.4	5	Challenge to integrate the different components into one system	2	2	Coordination between partners and commonly designing technical infrastructure	Coordination
1.4	6	Lack of commitment for sustaining infrastructure after period 4	1	3	DANS committed to sustain the built infrastructure for at least five years.	Sustainability
1.4	7	Insufficient knowledge and consensus on explicit semantics of social-science metadata to develop a search interface with sufficient added value for social science researchers	2	3	Make use of existing standardisation efforts in the community, including the CESSDA metadata models and thesauri.	FAIR
Observatory						
2.1	1	High non-response in online data collections	3	2	Knowledge exchange and shared results of online data collection	Technical
2.1	2	Disruptions to fieldwork due to COVID	1	2	Most data collection has now been transferred to online only	Technical
2.1	3	Low cooperation between data scouts and wider ODISSEI ecosystem (e.g. Portal and SANE)	2	2	Data Scouts need to be well embedded within the ODISSEI community and aware of the value added by ODISSEI	Coordination
2.1	4	No further funding for data collections	2	3	The financing strategy must identify cost reduction measures and a new financing strategy and stimulate the respective survey communities to collaborate on funding applications	Sustainability
2.2	1	MCAL not embedded in wider ODISSEI community	2	3	Ensure regular contact between MCAL team and wider ODISSEI Tasks (see 4.7)	Coordination
2.2	2	Shifting investment and user requirements	3	2	The content analysis landscape is very dynamic, and an agile approach is therefore being adopted for its development	Low Demand
2.4	1	No other cohorts wanting to invest in linkage project	1	2	Through multiple consortia in NL we are well connected to approach PIs	Low Demand
2.4	2	Ethical barriers to linkage	1	3	See "Delay in signing legal documents" at task 1.3	Legal
2.4	3	Not possible to develop MZ-DZ algorithm	2	2	Develop analytical strategy (mixture models); explore linkage to databases of data on newborns	Technical
Laboratory						
3.3	1	Interest in ODISSEI LISS Calls is limited	1	3	Invest more efforts in advertising the Calls, and promotion of the possibilities the Calls offers	Low Demand
3.3	2	Interest in ODISSEI LISS Calls is overwhelming, leading to very low award rate	2	2	Make calls more thematically focused; merge funds for two calls; limit the target population to e.g. early career researchers only	High Demand
3.3	3	Attrition LISS panel is non-random making the panel less representative of the Dutch (speaking) population	2	3	Intensify panel care; correct for biases with stratified refreshment samples; increase efforts to minimise attrition; if needed reallocate budget to fund additional refreshment samples	Technical

Task	#	Risk	Prob ⁶	Imp ⁷	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
3.3	4	Response rates decrease in monthly questionnaires and experiments fielded in the LISS panel	2	2	Motivate respondents to participate using response-enhancing measures, e.g. attractiveness of questionnaires and experiments, higher monetary incentives	Technical
3.3	5	Many panel members stop participating due to personal data breaches	1	3	Continuously monitor data security. Act proactively in case of a personal data breach or data leak	Legal
3.3	6	Increasing number of respondents opt-out when asked permission to link LISS data to register data, making linking less attractive for scientific research	2	2	Better explain what linking entails and that no identifying information will be made public	Technical
3.3	7	Delay in dissemination data via the LISS Data Archive due to restricted personnel capacity	1	2	Increase capacity; prioritise disseminations (first disseminate modules core study, then ODISSEI LISS Call projects, followed by other projects)	FAIR
3.3	8	Funding via the Domeinplan-SSH stops	1	3	Intensify efforts to acquire external funding	Sustainability
3.3	9	Insufficient alignment with the Portal team	3	3	Joint working group; funds made available	Coordination
Hub						
4.1	1	Researchers are hard to reach and/or too busy	2	3	The team will keep events concise. The team will make information easily accessible online.	Coordination
4.1	2	Community Managers do not have enough scientific knowledge	2	2	The team will have regular meetings with the entire Coordination Team, to keep up to date.	Staffing
4.1	3	An overload of ODISSEI communication, which lessens the interest of potential users.	1	2	The team will keep track of communication output in a Content Calendar.	Low Demand
4.2	1	Researchers are hard to reach and/or too busy	2	3	The education team will keep ODISSEI events concise. It will strive to match what it offers to researchers' needs and concentrate efforts in an intensive summer school.	Low Demand
4.2	2	Task team members do not have enough scientific knowledge	2	2	Regular meetings between task team and Coordination Team. It will work closely with partners who do have specific knowledge.	Staffing
4.2	3	Demand for courses is too high	2	2	The task team will scale up events, and when needed it will assist in coordinating 'train the trainer' events with ODISSEI partners.	High Demand
4.2	4	Demand for training is too low	2	3	The task team will work with the Community Management task (4.1) to increase ODISSEI's visibility. Integration in SICSS (task 4.5)	Low Demand
4.3	1	Not obtaining appropriate time investments from researchers	1	3	Selection of researchers based on time commitment	Coordination
4.3	2	Not reaching the non-academic researchers (e.g. planbureaus)	3	1	None (not actively seeking out collabs, but open to them); reusability of software products ->	Coordination

Task	#	Risk	Prob ⁶	Imp ⁷	Mitigating Action	Risk Area
					possibility of usage outside academia (see ASReview)	
4.3	3	Not being able to keep the team's knowledge state of the art	3	2	No person on earth has state-of-the-art knowledge. Mitigation is continuing training & education in collaboration with UU Information & Technology Services (ITS) and NLeScC; collaboration with experts in our network (e.g. UU focus area ADS)	Staffing
4.3	4	In the team, not being able to cover the wide range of required skills	1	3	(1) By spending 1 FTE on the wide expertise of UU ITS team, wide range of skills available; (2) network of experts in UU focus area ADS (3) participating in SIGs of NLeSC.	Staffing
4.3	5	Not finding sufficient projects	2	3	Active acquisition, close collaboration with community management, close collaboration with operational management	Low Demand
4.4	1	Fewer applications than expected	2	2	Allocate the remaining available money to the next call round to award more grants than initially planned.	Low Demand
4.4	2	Not reaching sufficient social scientists	2	3	Collaborating with the ODISSEI community managers to plan and organise an information day regarding the call for social science researchers. Enhance visibility through newsletters and social media.	Coordination
4.4	3	More applications than expected	2	2	Move funding forward to grant more projects, and acquire more funding for periods 2 & 3. Limit the scope of the calls, for example by using a thematic call, focussing on specific technologies (e.g., geospatial, visual analytics, etc.)	High Demand
4.4	4	Projects that are too complex to fit within the available hours	2	2	Organise information day and consultations hours with NLeSC and SoDa teams to advise on a fitting project plan.	Sustainability
4.5	1	Benchmarking platform doesn't sufficiently work	2	3	Early released of the software; embedding the technical team in the project team	Technical

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